

THE HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE AND PLACE OF THE FIRE CULT

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This article provides a scientific theoretical analysis of the ancient beliefs associated with fire and the symbolic meanings of people's belief in fire. Fire-related rituals, their causes and traditions are summarized based on the results of scientific research by research scientists. Figurative images related to the cult of fire were given, which were taken as a separate object of study.

Key words: Fire, fire, ash, charcoal, smoke, furnace, wood, shamanism,, hell, purification, mistress of fire, ceremonial fire, sacrifice, Zoroaster.

One of the oldest human inventions in the universe is fire. To be more precise, nature has shown its power, and in this sense, the ancients first preserved it for a long time as a result of careful care, and under the influence of fire, their thinking begins to change. They then create a Sunni fire with their intellect. I think the role of the sun in the emergence of the Fire Cult is unique in the first place. Ethnographer YV Ivanova in her article "Ceremonial Folklore" said that for ancient people, the sun was the sky, lightning was the fire between the earth and the sky, and they were always in contact. . [1] Some scholars write that the cross, a symbol of Christianity, is also believed to have originated from an ancient device made to create fire. .] .Do not insult the fire, do not leave the firewood in a dirty state. In such cases it is necessary to dry or wash it in the sun. The people also express the meaning of the child through the symbol of fire. This can be confirmed by the example of the names Gulkhan, Oloviddin, Otashboy, which are given to children. However, later the meaning of the child was transferred from the image of fire to the image of the lamp, which is his attribute. This is why it is often said that parents call their children "my lamp". This refers to the habit of children to be a beacon to the spirit of parents. So, the meaning of the proverb "A boy lights a lamp and a girl lights it" is that when a girl gets married and has a child, her parents' name and lamp do not go out. The first species to use fire and fire in the world was Homo erectus, which gained significant advantages in survival over its direct competitors. Initially, it is believed that they used the fire for natural reasons, such as lightning in a storm. One of the most important effects of discovering fire was the growth of this mind. Since you were able to cook the meat, it was easier to take it. The amount of nutrients increased and therefore increased the capacity of the brain. Therefore, by the end of the Late Paleolithic people in

their present form began to appear. [4] Now, according to an analysis of fire mentioned in the Avesta, the rarest source of the peoples of Central Asia, at the University of London, led by Mary Boys, it seems: It is a common custom in Iran to keep a fire burning in every house. "He also quotes Xenophon as saying that in his time there were no Persian temples, only a fire for worship. [5] However, no holiday, ceremony or the ceremony cannot take place without fire, which is the symbol of the main Zoroastrian god Ahura Mazda. The worship of fire was a symbol of Arta. , the sacred fire ("high benefit") burns in these temples. - Dedicated from November 16 to December 15. The main ritual performed by Zoroastrians in the sacred fire is "Yasna". Yasna means "worship" or "sacred service." A part of the Zoroastrian holy book, the Avesto, is called Yasna, which contains sacred texts that Zoroastrians read during prayer. [6] The Yasna is performed both by individual order of the believers and (often) on the occasion of one of the six "gahanbar" - the traditional great Zoroastrian holidays. Yasna is always performed by at least two priests in the morning. The service is held in a special room, where there is a table spread on the floor or a grass-covered part of the floor. During the service, a variety of things with a specific symbolic meaning are used, primarily fire (usually lit from the temple fire), for which fragrant wood, water, milk, pomegranate twigs, flowers, fruits, and so on are used. Before praying directly, the priests perform the rites of purification, both for the priest himself and for the things he uses in the ceremony. Purification is done with water from a well located in each Zoroastrian temple. The greatest sins were: burning the body with fire, defiling or extinguishing the sacred fire. [7] According to Zoroastrians, the human soul passes through the Chinwat Bridge (in Islam it is called the Pulisirot Bridge, and among the people it is called the Qil Bridge) over the hell to the afterlife, and passes through the question and answer of the true god Rashnu (Munkar-Nakir question in Islam). They weigh the good and evil deeds of man (good and evil) and send him to either heaven or hell, depending on the outcome. There will be no disaster, no pain. Hell, on the other hand, is a dark, cold place, with a constant fire burning. That is why people always long to go to heaven. The book of Yasna begins with Ashah - Praising the Truth, praising it, praying, glorifying the fire-guarding god Azar, religious leaders and other gods, beings. [8] The motto of the Avesto - good thoughts, good words and good deeds - is also applauded in the Yasna section. While applauding these three types of virtues, Zoroaster states his purpose, saying, "I turn away from all evil thoughts, evil words, and evil deeds" (p. 34), and emphasizes that he is a Mazdaist, a

Zoroastrian, an enemy of giants, and an Ahura. [9] In general, fire researchers in Zoroastrian temples are of three types:

The first is the Flame of Fire Bahrom, which was consecrated by kings and priests in Adurian

The second is religious ceremonies with the participation of priests and devout believers in Dori Mihr.

The third is a fire dedicated to the spirits of their ancestors

The role of fire in the development of society is compared and analyzed with its types.

1 - fire from the funeral;

2- fire used by the dye;

3- fire from the houses of the ruler and the representative of the authorities;

4- fire using pottery;

5- fire used by the brick manufacturer;

6 Fire from the abode of the poor (beggar) or ascetic;

7 The fire used by the jeweler;

8 fire, used in engraving;

9 Fire used by blacksmiths,

10 bullets, used by the gunman;

11 The fire used by the baker;

12 fire, used by a holy drink maker, distiller, or pagan;

13 - fire used by the military or travelers;

14 - fire used by the shepherd;

15 Fire caused by natural lightning;

16 - The fire of the house or the fire of the house of any Zoroastrian.

The worship of fire is one of the oldest cults. We can see this in the Jarkoton monument, which is the symbol of the First City in the Surkhandarya oasis and the first temple, especially the fire temple, as well as in the Gonur monument in the territory of Southern Turkmenistan. In short, fire is one of the four elements

that form the basis of Zoroastrianism, and fire is also one of the natural factors that form the basis of Zoroastrianism. The reason is that the sun stands at the base and base of the fire is a symbol of greatness. [10] The Zoroastrians used fire as a mediator for their prayers. It was believed that the flame of the fire ascending to heaven would convey the prayers and supplications in prayer to God. [11] The highest form of fire is the sacred fire that stands beside me in the fire.

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